

ETIMOLOGY OF THE TERM "CONJUNCTION"

Boxodirova Farog'at Xamidxonovna

Master degree, Uychi district N21

+998934058515

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13922968>

Abstract: In this thesis the term of ETIMOLOGY is discussed and analysed. Some detailed informations are looked through.

Key words: ETIMOLOGY, speech, conjunction, century, type of conjunctions

Аннотация: В данной диссертации обсуждается и анализируется термин ЭТИМОЛОГИЯ. Просматривается некоторая подробная информация.

Ключевые слова: ЭТИМОЛОГИЯ, речь, союз, столетие, тип союза.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu dissertatsiyada ETIMOLOGIYA atamasi muhokama qilinadi va tahlil qilinadi. Ba'zi batafsil ma'lumotlar ko'rib chiqiladi.

Tayanch iboralar: ETIMOLOGIYA, nutq, bog'lovchi, asr, bog'lovchi turi.

Beginning in the 17th century, an element of a conjunction was known as a conjunct. A conjunction itself was then called a connective. That archaic term, however, diminished in usage during the early 20th century.

Conjunctions are one of the most **important** parts of speech, yet they are often misunderstood. There are three types of conjunctions: coordinating, subordinating, and correlative. Each type has a specific purpose in writing.

conjunction (countable and uncountable, plural conjunctions)

The act of joining, or condition of being joined. quotations "synonyms"

Synonyms: connection, union

(grammar) A word used to join other words or phrases together into sentences. The specific conjunction used shows how the two joined parts are related. quotations

Cooccurrence; coincidence. quotations

(astronomy) The alignment of two bodies in the solar system such that they have the same longitude when seen from Earth. quotations "antonym" "hyponyms"

Antonym: opposition

(astrology) An aspect in which planets are in close proximity to one another.

(logic) The proposition resulting from the combination of two or more propositions using the Δ () operator. coordinate term, meronyms

A place where multiple things meet quotations

(obsolete) Sexual intercourse. quotations "synonyms"

Dictionary entries near conjunction: Conjoint, conjugal, conjugate, conjugation, conjunct, conjunction, conjunctiva, conjunctive, conjunctivitis, conjuncture, conjuration

A conjunction (abbreviated here cnj.) is a type of word that connects two words, sentences, phrases or clauses together, and shows something about their relationship to each other.

There are three groups of conjunctions: coordinating conjunctions, correlative conjunctions, and subordinating conjunctions. Coordinating conjunctions join two or more items of equal importance together, like the Modern English words "and", "or", "but", and others. Correlative conjunctions are like coordinating conjunctions in that they also join two or more equal items, but they work in groups, like the Modern English words "either... or...", "neither... nor...", "both... and...", and more. Subordinating conjunctions are conjunctions that join items of unequal importance, for example Modern English "because", "although", "unless", and more.

Here are some important Old English coordinating conjunctions:

and - and
ac - but
ne - nor
opþe - or

WOC
WORLD
ONLINE
CONFERENCES

